

A SIMPLE FREQUENCY SELECTIVE SURFACE (FSS) WITH BIO-INSPIRED ELEMENT GEOMETRY FOR WIRELESS APPLICATIONS

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Abstract - With each passing day, the demand for more efficient telecommunications systems that guarantee the rapid exchange of information increases. In this scenario, this work aims to present a Frequency Selective Surface (FSS) design proposal with bio-inspired element geometry to filter the frequency spectrum for wireless communication systems operating around 2.4 GHz.

Keywords: FSS; Wireless; Bio-Inspired FSS; Bluetooth; Wi-Fi.

INTRODUCTION

Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSSs) are planar and periodic structures composed of conductive patch or aperture elements. Due to their ability to filter certain frequency bands, FSSs are known as spatial filters. Among their applications, wireless communication systems, radomes, antennas, among others, stand out [1] [2].

There are several factors that influence the frequency response of an FSS, such as the geometry of the unit cell, the periodicity of the structure, the type of element (patch or aperture), the polarization of the incident wave, and the characteristics of the dielectric material [3]. As a result, in recent years, bio-inspired element geometries have been introduced, inspired by natural shapes, which have shown satisfactory results in filtering frequency spectra for wireless systems [4].

Therefore, this article proposes an FSS whose objective is to filter the frequency spectrum for wireless systems operating around 2.4 GHz, such as 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi (IEEE 802.11b/g standards) and Bluetooth.

DEVELOPMENT

The proposed FSS, computationally designed and constructed, was based on the bio-inspired shape of an eight-petal flower, as can be seen in Fig. 1, which displays the unit cell with the element's geometry.

Figure 1 – Unit cell with the geometry of the element.

The geometry used is motivated by [5], where the authors proposed the use of the Gielis formula, which is shown in Eq. 1 [6]. In Eq. 1, the argument $m/4$ of the angle ϕ is responsible for inserting the chosen symmetry pattern. In addition, n_i and $m \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (set of positive real numbers), and $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^+_{\neq 0}$ (set of non-zero positive real numbers) [6].

$$r(\phi) = \frac{1}{\left\{ \left[\left(\frac{1}{a} \cos\left(\phi \frac{m}{4}\right) \right)^{n_2} + \left(\frac{1}{b} \sin\left(\phi \frac{m}{4}\right) \right)^{n_3} \right]^{\frac{1}{n_1}} \right\}} \quad (1)$$

The Gielis formula is widely used in generating geometric patterns that follow the shape of plants or other living organisms, such as flowers and leaves [6].

The structure is characterized by a height of approximately 74.412mm and a width of 15.41123mm between the petals.

The structure's periodicity is 80.613mm, and the dielectric substrate used was FR4 Epoxy, which has a relative permittivity of 4.4, a dielectric loss tangent of 0.02, and a thickness of 1.6mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The method used to simulate the simple structure was the Method of Moments (MOM), and its result is shown in Fig. 2. Initially, it can be observed that the structure's response is independent of polarization, as it exhibits the same behavior for waves incident on the electric and magnetic fields.

Also, in Fig. 2, it can be seen that the generated filtering band has a bandwidth of 560 MHz, starting at 2.11 GHz and ending at 2.67 GHz. Furthermore, its resonance frequency occurs at 2.43 GHz. The current distribution on the element, when it reaches the resonance frequency, can be seen in Fig. 3.

Figure 2 – Simulated results obtained in terms of transmission coefficient.

Figure 3 – Simulated current distribution at 2.43 GHz.

Based on the result presented in Fig. 2, it is concluded that the proposed FSS is capable of filtering the application bands of 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi and Bluetooth. Wireless technologies that use IEEE 802.11b/g standards operate in the frequency range from 2.4 to 2.484 GHz, while those using Bluetooth operate in the 2.4 to 2.4835 GHz band [7]. The filtering of these bands is shown in Fig. 4. Note that in the following figure, -10 dB insertion loss was taken as the Reference Level (RL) for transmission.

Figure 4 – Filtering of the 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi and Bluetooth frequency bands.

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